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A novel SPECT-based approach reveals early mechanisms of central and peripheral inflammation after cerebral ischemia

Krisztián Szigeti¹, Ildikó Horváth¹, Dániel S Veres¹, Bernadett Martinecz³, Nikolett Lénárt³, Noémi Kovács², Erika Bakcsa¹, Alexa Márta¹, Mariann Semjéni², Domokos Máthé², Ádám Dénes^{3,*}

1. Department of Biophysics and Radiation Biology, Semmelweis University, Budapest, Hungary

2. CROmed Translational Research Centers, Budapest, Hungary

3. Laboratory of Neuroimmunology, Institute of Experimental Medicine, Budapest, Hungary

*Correspondence: Dr. Adam Denes, Laboratory of Neuroimmunology, Institute of Experimental Medicine, 1083 Budapest, Szigony u. 43., Hungary

Email: denesa@koki.hu

Phone: +36 12109954

Short title: SPECT reveals early changes after stroke

Inflammation that develops in the brain and peripheral organs after stroke contributes profoundly to poor outcome of patients. However, mechanisms through which inflammation impacts on brain injury and overall outcome are improperly understood, in part because the earliest inflammatory events after brain injury are not revealed by current imaging tools. Here we show that single-photon emission computed tomography (NanoSPECT/CT Plus) allows visualization of blood brain barrier (BBB) injury after experimental stroke well before changes can be detected with MRI. Early ^{99m}Tc-DTPA signal changes predict infarct development and systemic inflammation preceding experimental stroke leads to very early perfusion deficits and increased BBB injury within 2 h after the onset of ischemia. Acute brain injury also leads to peripheral inflammation and immunosuppression, which contribute to poor outcome of stroke patients. SPECT imaging revealed early (within 2 h) changes in perfusion, barrier function and inflammation in the lungs and the gut after experimental stroke, with good predictive value for the development of histopathological changes at later time points. Collectively, visualisation of early inflammatory changes stroke could open new translational research avenues to elucidate the interactions between central and peripheral inflammation and to evaluate *in vivo* „multi-system” effects of putative anti-inflammatory treatments.

Keywords: SPECT imaging, brain injury, systemic inflammation, cerebral ischemia, BBB

Introduction

Stroke is the leading cause of permanent disability worldwide and represents a huge socio-economic burden.¹ Treatment opportunities are currently limited to tissue plasminogen activator (tPA), which is available for the minority of stroke patients.² Recent data indicate that common comorbidities for stroke (atherosclerosis, diabetes, obesity or infection) are associated with an elevated systemic inflammatory burden and, since inflammation both in the brain and in the periphery contributes to poor clinical outcome^{3,4}, interest has focused on anti-inflammatory therapies.⁵ Since neurons die rapidly during ischemia⁶, decision making in the clinic largely relies on early imaging data from CT or MRI. However, these essential imaging tools give little information about inflammatory changes in the brain and do not reveal earliest signs of blood brain barrier (BBB) injury after stroke that could be negatively influenced by systemic inflammation.^{3,7} Therefore, development of novel imaging approaches could largely support translational research and development of personalized therapies. Stroke and other forms of acute brain injury also result in systemic immunosuppression, which often leads to post-stroke infections. Infectious complications that affect the lungs or the urinary tract contribute profoundly to mortality and poor recovery of stroke patients.⁸ In addition, stroke patients often present with diverse gut-associated symptoms such as paralytic ileus and translocation of gut bacteria after stroke has been documented.⁹⁻¹¹ However, it is currently unclear whether brain injury has organ-specific effects which could be revealed with imaging techniques *in vivo*.

Single photon emission tomography (SPECT) has been used previously to visualize cerebral blood flow and BBB injury in patients 24-72h after stroke.^{12, 13} Penetration of Tc-99m-diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid (DTPA) into the brain parenchyma after injury allows the

assessment of BBB breakdown, whereas hexamethylpropylene amine oxime (HMPAO) radioligands are taken up by brain tissue proportionally to cerebral blood flow, which allows for monitoring of perfusion changes.¹⁴ In addition, radiolabelled human serum albumin (HSA) has been used previously to visualize plasma extravasation and inflammation in the brain.¹⁵ However, early events of BBB injury and perfusion changes have not been investigated by SPECT in clinical or experimental stroke studies and the predictive value of SPECT imaging for infarct evolution and the development of central or peripheral inflammation after brain injury are not known. Here we reveal a previously unrecognised potential for SPECT imaging in translational stroke research. First, we developed novel SPECT-based imaging approaches in a mouse model of experimental stroke that show remarkable sensitivity and allow early visualization of BBB injury with strong predictive value for infarct evolution. Second, we show that SPECT imaging reveals mechanisms through which preceding systemic inflammation has very early and detrimental effects on acute brain injury. Third, this is the first *in vivo* imaging study to identify brain injury-induced changes in peripheral organs that are most commonly affected in stroke patients, within 2 hours after experimental stroke. These novel imaging protocols make use of clinically approved radioligands, and give sufficient resolution in the small mouse brain, thus could facilitate the understanding of inflammatory events after stroke and translation of experimental data to clinical benefit.

Materials and Methods

Animals

Experiments were carried out in adult male C57BL/6J mice (n=39) aged 12-16 weeks, breeding in the SPF unit of the Institute of Experimental Medicine (IEM). Animals were allowed free access to food and water and maintained under temperature, humidity and light-controlled conditions. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ARRIVE guidelines and the guidelines set by the European

Communities Council Directive (86/609 EEC) and approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of the IEM and the Semmelweis University (XIV-I-001/29-7/2012).

Middle Cerebral Artery Occlusion (MCAo)

MCAo was performed using the intraluminal filament technique as described earlier.^{16, 17} In brief, animals were anaesthetised with isoflurane and a silicone-coated monofilament (210 µm tip diameter, Doccol, US) was introduced to the left external carotid artery and advanced along the internal carotid artery to occlude the MCA for 30 or 45min. Different occlusion times were used to produce both small striatal infarcts (30min MCAo) as well as striatal and cortical injury (45min MCAo) in order to assess the sensitivity of SPECT imaging to perfusion deficits and BBB injury changes after experimental stroke. During surgery, core temperature was maintained at 37±0.5°C. Sham animals were anaesthetised for the same period of time and all surgical procedures were identical to the stroke group except that the filament was not advanced to the MCA. In a group of animals cerebral blood flow was assessed by a laser Doppler (Moor Instruments, UK). After experimental stroke, 4 mice were excluded pre hoc due to incomplete occlusion of the MCA (lack of striatal infarction, n=2) and surgical artifacts (subarachnoid haemorrhage, n=1; vagus injury n=1). 2 further mice died (24h and 48h after LPS and MCAo, respectively).

Systemic inflammation

Systemic inflammation was induced by intraperitoneal injection of lipopolysaccharide (LPS, serotype: 0111:B4, Sigma L4391, 40 µg/kg) 3h prior to experimental stroke as described earlier.¹⁸

SPECT and MRI

Multimodal imaging studies were conducted with multiple radiotracers in different time points following MCAo. During the acquisitions mice were placed in prone position in a dedicated mouse bed, and were anesthetized with 2% isoflurane in oxygen. 63 ± 4 MBq Tc^{99m} -DTPA or Tc^{99m} -HMPAO was administered intravenously via tail vein injection followed by an anatomical T2-weighted MRI scan. An hour after the isotope administration – mice remaining in the same bed and position – a whole body CT and afterwards a whole body SPECT scan was started. A group of mice were pre-scanned 7 days prior to MCAo to assess baseline DTPA binding. Mice were scanned 2h after MCAo for Tc^{99m} -DTPA or Tc^{99m} -HMPAO uptake. One day after MCAo 22 ± 3 MBq I^{125} -HSA administration was embedded in the above protocol right before the SPECT-CT imaging. Duration of anaesthesia and all treatment protocols were identical in the sham and the stroke group during and after imaging.

MRI measurements were performed on a nanoScan 1 T MRI system (Mediso Ltd., Budapest, Hungary) equipped with an actively shielded 450 mT/m gradient system and volume coils for both receiving and transmitting. As anatomical imaging a T2-weighted FSE (fast spin echo) sequence was acquired with three-dimensional acquisition scheme having the squared axial FOV 42 mm and the in plane resolution of 0.3 mm, the same as the slice thickness. Imaging parameters were TR/TE 2200/92.8 ms, 25 μ s dwell time and 2 excitations resulting in a 35-minute-scan. A diffusion weighted spin echo (DWI-SE) scan followed the anatomical scan. Ten axial slices were acquired with 1 mm slice thickness (0.2 mm gap between the slices) and in plane resolution of 0.4 mm. To calculate mean apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) map diffusion weighting was created in three orthogonal directions with the below parameters: TR/TE 600/18 ms, Δ/δ 2.4/10 ms and two different b-values of (1; 600) s/mm².

SPECT-CT measurements were performed on NanoSPECT/CT+ (MedisoLtd., Budapest, Hungary) equipped with multi-pinhole mouse collimators. The semicircular CT scanning was acquired with 45 kV tube voltage, 500 ms of exposure time, 1:4

binning and 360 projections in 9 minutes. In the reconstruction 0.16 mm in plane resolution and slice thickness were set and Butterworth filter was applied. Whole body SPECT scanning was carried out with 45 frames per cycle and termination condition of 135 s per frame in a scan range of 96.6 mm resulting in a 100-minute-scan. The detection peak energies were set to 24 keV in case of I^{125} and 140.51 keV in case of Tc^{99m} with a 20% energy window. Two different SPECT reconstruction was done concerning the resolution: 0.45 mm isovoxel in case of the whole body and 0.3 mm isovoxel in a reduced FOV centered to the head only. Data from SPECT measurements in the brain were presented as a ratio to cerebellum, which brain region was not affected by cerebral ischemia and levels of ^{99m}Tc -HMPAO, ^{99m}Tc -DTPA and I^{125} -HSA remained unaltered throughout the study. Peripheral SPECT imaging data are presented as a percentage of whole body radioactivity.

Tissue processing

Under terminal anaesthesia animals were perfused transcardially with saline followed by paraformaldehyde (PFA; 4% in PBS). Brains were post-fixed in 4% PFA at 4 °C for 24 h, and cryoprotected in sucrose/PBS. 25 μ m thick coronal brain sections were cut on a sledge microtome (Leica SM2010R). Gut and lung tissues were embedded into paraffin and 5 μ m thick sections were cut (Leica SM2010R) prior to Haematoxylin and Eosin (HE) and periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) alcian blue staining.

Measurement of infarct volume and neurological outcome

The volume of ischaemic brain damage was measured on cresyl violet stained brain sections and corrected for oedema as described previously.¹⁶ Neurological status in mice was assessed according to a neurological grading score of increasing severity of deficit¹⁹: 0, no observable deficit; 1, torso flexion to right; 2, spontaneous circling to right; 3, leaning/falling to right; 4, no spontaneous movement.

Immunohistochemistry and Immunofluorescence

Leakage of plasma derived IgG (BBB damage) was detected with biotinylated horse anti-mouse IgG (Vector, 1:500) followed by incubation with ABCsolution (Vector, 1:500). The colour was developed by diaminobenzidinetetrahydrochloride (DAB). Immunofluorescence was performed as described earlier¹⁶, using rat anti-mouse CD45 1:200 (Serotec, UK) and rabbit anti-Iba1 1:1000 (Wako Chemicals, Germany) primary antibodies followed by fluorochrome-conjugated donkey anti-rat Alexa594 and donkey anti-rabbit Alexa488 antisera (1:500, Invitrogen, UK). Activated microglia (Iba1+, CD45^{low} ramified cells with thickened processes and enlarged cell body) and recruited leukocytes (CD45 highly expressing round or elongated cells) were counted in the striatum, cerebral cortex, hippocampus and thalamus on 4 serial sections rostro-caudally (2-2 fields per section).

Quantitative analysis and statistics

Mice were randomly assigned to experimental groups. All quantitative analysis was performed under blinded conditions. CD45-positive cells were quantified in two randomly selected fields on 3-3 coronal brain sections each according to bregma to cover the striatum, the cerebral cortex, the hippocampus and the thalamus. Normality

of data sets was assessed with Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Parametric data were analysed with Student's t test or two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's post hoc comparison (GraphPadPrism6.0). Neurological scores were analysed with Mann Whitney test. Linear regression was performed with GraphPadPrism6.0. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

SPECT imaging reveals early events of BBB injury in the brain after experimental stroke with predictive value for infarct development

To visualize early changes in perfusion, BBB injury and inflammation after experimental stroke, we used SPECT / CT imaging with combination of radioligands ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO or ^{99m}Tc-DTPA with ¹²⁵I-HSA. HMPAO signal was significantly decreased in the ipsilateral striatum and cerebral cortex 2h after MCAo whereas no changes were seen in mice subjected to sham surgery (Fig.1 A-D). Laser Doppler confirmed that this effect was not due to incomplete reperfusion after MCAo since cerebral blood flow in the MCA area returned to baseline levels within 5min after the withdrawal of the filament (Fig.1C). HMPAO signal did not show significant difference 24h after MCAo compared to that of sham animals, but was significantly lower after 72h reperfusion (Fig.1 E). Using SPECT imaging, we found increased DTPA signal in the ipsilateral striatum as early as 2h after 30min MCAo, in overlapping areas with leakage of plasma derived IgG (indicative of BBB breakdown) as detected on coronal brain sections (Fig.1 F-G). No changes in the ipsilateral hemisphere were detectable with MRI using T2 (Supplementary Figure 1) or DWI (not shown) 2h after MCAo. 24h after 30min MCAo, a regimen that leads to mostly striatal infarcts, DTPA signal was increased in the ipsilateral striatum, whereas DTPA uptake was extended to the cerebral cortex after 45min MCAo, a regimen that leads to both striatal and cortical infarction, as confirmed by MRI and SPECT coregistration (Fig.1H). DTPA uptake in the striatum at 2h reperfusion showed good correlation ($R^2=0.57$, $P=0.031$) with infarct size measured on cresyl violet-stained brain sections 24h after MCAo (Fig.1I). 24h after MCAo, DTPA uptake was significantly increased in the ipsilateral striatum in mice with an infarction larger than 20mm³ compared to sham animals (Fig. 1J), and showed a significant correlation ($R^2=0.55$, $P=0.022$) with BBB injury as measured by leakage of plasma-derived IgG into the brain on coronal brain sections (Fig.

1K), irrespective of infarct size. No changes in I125-HSA uptake was seen in the brain after experimental stroke up to 24h reperfusion (not shown).

SPECT imaging reveals early detrimental effects of systemic inflammation on cerebral perfusion and BBB injury after experimental stroke

Since we found that central HMPAO and DTPA signal changes revealed early events of cerebral perfusion and BBB injury, we used these novel imaging protocols to investigate the impact of systemic inflammation on brain injury after stroke. Systemic inflammation induced by intraperitoneal administration of LPS 2h prior to 30min MCAo reduced cerebral perfusion in the ipsilateral cortex (by 17% in the cerebral cortex, $P=0.048$ and by 25% in the MCA area, $P=0.0067$, as measured by ^{99m}Tc -HMPAO uptake), compared to stroke alone. No changes were seen in the striatum or the thalamus (Fig.1A-C). Systemic inflammation resulted in increased DTPA uptake in the ipsilateral hemisphere as early as 2h after reperfusion ($P<0.001$), which was most apparent in the cortical MCA area (36% higher compared to stroke alone, Fig2D-E). The effect of systemic inflammation on increased DTPA uptake in the brain was also seen 24h after reperfusion ($P<0.01$, Fig. 2F). Systemic inflammation did not increase DTPA uptake after stroke in the core of the infarct (striatum), but a significantly higher DTPA uptake was found at 24h reperfusion compared to the 2h time point ($P<0.05$), indicating the development of larger BBB injury over time (Fig. 2G). No changes in the ipsilateral hemisphere were detectable with MRI 2h after MCAo and preceding systemic inflammation (Supplementary Figure 1).

Systemic inflammation increases brain inflammation after stroke and leads to markedly impaired neurological outcome

We found that increased DTPA uptake in the ipsilateral hemisphere was associated with increased microglial activation (Fig. 3A, B) after experimental stroke in mice with preceding

systemic inflammation. There was a marked increase in leukocyte recruitment within the MCA area of the ipsilateral cerebral cortex in response to systemic inflammation after stroke (Fig. 3B, C; 0.1 ± 0.1 cells after stroke and 3.4 ± 1.5 cells after systemic inflammation and stroke). There was a trend towards increased infarct size (Fig. 3D, not significant), whereas profoundly impaired neurological outcome was observed in mice with preceding systemic inflammation (Fig. 3E), in accordance with our previous findings.¹⁸

SPECT imaging reveals early events of inflammation and perfusion changes in the lung after experimental stroke

Since infectious complications that manifest in the lung, the gut or the urinary tract are critical contributors to poor outcome and survival of stroke patients⁸, we assessed whether our novel SPECT imaging protocols reveal early changes in these organs after experimental stroke. ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO signal showed a marked increase in the lung as early as 2h after experimental stroke, which was most apparent in the upper lobes of the lung (Fig. 4A, B), to different extent in individual mice. Lung inflammation was also evident in mice showing the highest HMPAO uptake in MRI (Fig. 4B). HMPAO signal showed a significant increase 24h after MCAo in the upper lobes of the lung (Fig. 4C) compared to sham mice (by 50%, $P=0.027$, Fig.4D). Similarly to HMPAO, 24h after experimental stroke I125-HSA signal increased significantly in the lung compared to sham mice (by 27%, $P=0.011$), which was most apparent in the upper lobes of the lung (71% increase over sham mice, $P=0.003$). There was a good correlation between HSA and HMPAO signal increases in individual mice 24h after stroke ($R^2=0.64$), whereas only 20% of the mice showed any changes in the lung based on CT or MR images of those having increased HSA or HMPAO uptake in the upper lobes of the lung (not shown). No significant difference in lung DTPA signal was found between sham and stroke mice. Histological analysis identified inflammatory changes (alveolar space collapse, edema) in the lungs after stroke at 24h reperfusion (Fig.4H). This

was not seen in sham animals. 72h after MCAo 30% of the animals developed pneumonia based on microhaemorrhages and increased mucus production in the lungs as assessed on Haematoxylin and Eosin- and periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) alcian blue –stained lung sections (Fig.4h).

Experimental stroke leads to rapid gut barrier function changes that can be detected in vivo by SPECT

Stroke patients have diverse gut associated symptoms, including constipation, reduced bowel motility, paralytic ileus and dysphagia, whereas bacterial translocation from the gut to the circulation has also been documented after stroke.^{9-11, 20} However, no *in vivo* imaging studies demonstrated previously that acute brain injury results in robust and rapid changes in the gut and gave insight into the mechanisms. SPECT imaging with ^{99m}Tc-DTPA revealed early and transient changes in the gut after experimental stroke as identified by increases in DTPA signal 2h after reperfusion (by 64%, $P=0.025$, Fig.5 A-C), which recovered fully by 24h reperfusion (Fig. 5C). No perfusion changes were detected in the gut after MCAo as identified by ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO. Histological analysis on haematoxylin and eosin-stained gut tissues has not revealed any obvious sign of tissue injury or inflammatory infiltrates after experimental stroke (Fig. 5D), suggesting that brain injury-induced effects alone could be insufficient to cause lasting gut inflammation. Since bacterial cell wall products released to the circulation after stroke could facilitate gut inflammation and also contribute to systemic inflammatory changes, we have investigated gut DTPA signal changes in mice with preceding systemic inflammation. Systemic inflammation preceding stroke prolonged DTPA signal increases in the gut as suggested by increased DTPA uptake compared to mice that had undergone experimental stroke only (Fig. 5E), indicating that increased systemic inflammatory burden could facilitate brain injury-induced changes in the gut.

Discussion

In this research paper we reveal very early events of inflammation and injury in both the brain and peripheral organs after experimental stroke, using novel SPECT imaging approaches combined with CT and MRI. These new imaging protocols highlight a previously unrecognised potential for SPECT imaging to detect BBB injury within a clinically relevant time window, 2 hours after stroke with predictive value for infarct development. SPECT imaging revealed that systemic inflammation preceding experimental stroke leads rapidly to reduced cortical perfusion and increased BBB injury, primarily in penumbral tissues after induction of cerebral ischemia that is associated with markedly augmented brain inflammation and impaired neurological outcome. In addition, we show that SPECT-based imaging protocols can detect inflammatory changes in peripheral organs (the lungs and the gut) as early as 2 hours after stroke, which are frequently affected in stroke patients and this contributes profoundly to poor clinical outcome and worse recovery. Early inflammatory changes in the lungs as revealed by SPECT were followed by the development of pulmonary inflammation 24-72h later in experimental animals.

At present, the clinically accepted method in early diagnostic imaging of acute ischaemic stroke is the determination of perfusion-weighted imaging (PWI) / diffusion-weighted imaging (DWI) mismatch to identify the core and the penumbra. However, limitations of mismatch detection in both preclinical and clinical research has been recognised, especially in the context of comorbidities^{21, 22}, whilst early events of BBB injury are not assessed routinely in patients.

To our knowledge, this is the first study that used SPECT imaging to visualize early disruption of the BBB after experimental stroke. Earlier studies could detect BBB breakdown with MRI using Gadolinium-DTPA (Gd-DTPA) as contrast agent and with near-infrared fluorescence imaging (NIRF), using NIRF-BSA, 4-24 hours after focal cerebral ischemia in the rodent brain.²³⁻²⁶ So far, clinical imaging studies have assessed only delayed phases of BBB injury

with SPECT, using ^{99m}Tc-DTPA 48-72h after stroke [12](#), [27](#), [28](#), in which correlation between BBB injury and neurological outcome has been reported.¹² In our experimental model, DTPA uptake in the ipsilateral hemisphere 2h after stroke was predictive of infarct size measured at 24h reperfusion, particularly in the case of large infarcts. Importantly, early DTPA uptake was significantly augmented by preceding systemic inflammation, which was most apparent in penumbra, affecting the MCA area of the ipsilateral cerebral cortex. At present, assessment of detrimental systemic inflammatory processes in stroke patients largely relies on blood markers (increased white blood cell count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate or plasma C-reactive protein, CRP), whilst there are no imaging tools that could visualize systemic inflammation or its early effect on brain injury. Whole-body SPECT imaging could be used in experimental and clinical studies to determine *in vivo* regional differences in inflammatory activation in the brain and peripheral tissues, to address key research questions and improve the predictive value of blood biomarkers. We have shown earlier that in patients with multiple risk factors for stroke and chronically elevated CRP, brain inflammation (microglial activation as assessed by positron emission tomography) is apparent even prior to the occurrence of any acute cerebrovascular events, independently of any obvious neurological disease. Similar changes have been found in the brain in relevant co-morbid animal models.²⁹ Underlying systemic inflammation due to old age, chronic diseases or infection results in markedly impaired outcome after stroke in patients and in experimental animals.⁷, [16-18](#), [30](#) However, mechanisms by which systemic inflammation impacts on brain injury are improperly understood. Recent data suggest that peripheral inflammatory stimuli (induced by LPS or the proinflammatory cytokine interleukin-1) could alter cerebral perfusion, lead to larger BBB injury or cerebral oedema after stroke that might happen independently of increases in infarct size.¹⁸, [31](#), [32](#) In fact, we have found reduced ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO uptake in the cerebral cortex early (2 h) after experimental stroke that was further reduced by preceding systemic inflammation. In contrast, systemic inflammation did not significantly reduce cerebral perfusion and did not augment BBB injury in the striatum (infarct core), where

cerebral blood flow was maximally reduced during MCAo. HMPAO signal showed an increase to subnormal values after 24h reperfusion and dropped again by 72h post-stroke. The sole study that used ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO and SPECT in an MCAo model found similar reduction in HMPAO signal upon occlusion followed by a gradual increase between 2 days to 7 days post-reperfusion.³³ It is believed that the SPECT signal is derived from the accumulation of a hydrophilic metabolite of ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO in the brain parenchyma¹³, but HMPAO signal changes could also be due to elevated glutathione levels.³⁴ Inflammation could contribute to both reduced cerebral perfusion several hours after the induction of reperfusion following stroke (often termed as the „no-reflow phenomenon”) and increased levels of oxidative stress^{35, 36}, therefore mechanisms of HMPAO signal changes after stroke need to be investigated in detail in future studies. Measurements by laser Doppler have shown that blood flow in the MCA was fully restored upon the induction of reperfusion, however, this technique does not give information about whether reflow takes place at the level of capillaries in deeper brain tissues. Thus, HMPAO appears to be a sensitive marker of compromised blood flow after cerebral ischaemia in the brain parenchyma and correlations between HMPAO signal changes and tissue oxygenation will need to be investigated. Importantly, our SPECT imaging studies using ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO and histological data suggest that systemic inflammation has very early and negative impact on cerebral perfusion, inflammation and BBB injury, well within the relevant therapeutic time window after stroke, which indicates a good potential for anti-inflammatory therapies in patients with high systemic inflammatory burden. For example, therapeutic blockade of actions of IL-1, a key proinflammatory cytokine, was effective to prevent increased BBB injury, infarct size and worse neurological outcome induced by a human *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolate in mice and rats after experimental stroke.¹⁷

Brain injury induces profound inflammatory changes in the periphery in both patients and experimental animals that turns into immunosuppression. One of the most detrimental clinical consequences of post-stroke immunosuppression is the development of infectious

complications that lead to long hospitalisation, impaired recovery or death in patients.⁸ Our SPECT imaging results identify for the first time obvious changes in some of the most affected peripheral organs after stroke, namely in the lungs and the gut, as early as from 2 hours to 24 hours after acute experimental brain injury. At present, the precise cellular – molecular mechanisms underlying early 99mTc-HMPAO, 99mTc-DTPA and I125-HSA signal are currently unclear, but are likely to reflect alterations in inflammatory processes, perfusion and barrier-function. Uptake of 99mTc-HMPAO by bronchoalveolar cells in the inflamed lung of smokers or after lung toxicity is supposedly reflective of altered glutathione concentrations.³⁷ Our histological data confirmed the development of inflammation in the lung starting from 24h after experimental stroke. This is also supported by increased pulmonary uptake of I125-HSA after stroke. Constipation, dysphagia, paralytic ileus, digestion problems and other gut symptoms are often seen in stroke patients and bacterial translocation across the gut epithelium has also been reported.^{9-11, 20, 38} Since the gut barrier structures resemble those of the CNS³⁹ and 99mTc-DTPA identified early, but transient changes in the gut after stroke, whereas no changes in I125-HSA or 99mTc-HMPAO signal were observed, it is possible that 99mTc-DTPA signal increases are reflective of changes in the gut barrier structures in response to brain injury. The autonomic nervous system has been implicated in the development of post-stroke immunosuppression.^{8, 40} Both the gut and the lungs receive rich autonomic innervation that could directly dampen immune responses⁴¹, thus it is possible that brain injury induced changes in these organs are due to autonomic activation or lack of central autonomic control, however this must be functionally investigated in further studies. Nevertheless, currently no imaging tools can visualize early events of peripheral inflammation or infection after brain injury in patients or experimental animals, whilst early diagnosis of infection would have profound clinical benefits. Post-stroke infections are not only associated with a lower survival rate, but preventive antibacterial therapy is very effective to reduce infections after severe non-lacunar ischemic stroke.⁴²

Translation of experimental findings to clinical benefit is one of the biggest challenges of current research in the field of brain diseases. We have developed a set of new imaging applications using SPECT to investigate mechanisms of stroke-induced pathologies in mice. Whilst our imaging tools could be effectively used to understand mechanisms of brain diseases in experimental models, there is a good potential to translate these findings into clinical application. The image resolution used was sufficient to identify detailed functional and anatomical changes in different areas of the small mouse brain, which could be markedly improved in the human brain. In addition, we used radioligands that are already approved for clinical use, which may largely support clinical studies with the overall aim to develop protocols for improved diagnosis of disease.

In conclusion, we developed novel, SPECT-based imaging applications for complex assessment of inflammatory, perfusion and barrier function changes in experimental stroke that could support understanding of mechanisms of stroke and other brain diseases with good potential for clinical translation.

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Author Contributions

K.Sz. and A.D. designed research; K.Sz., I.H., D.S.V., B.M., N.L., N.K., E.B., A.M., M.S. and A.D. performed research; D.M. contributed new reagents/analytic tools;

K.Sz., I.H., D.S.V., B.M., N.L., N.K., E.B., A.M., M.S. and A.D. analyzed data; and
K.SZ, D.M. and A.D. wrote the paper.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Supplementary information

Supplementary information is available on JCBFM website.

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Figure legends

Figure 1. SPECT imaging reveals early events of BBB injury after experimental stroke.

A. Experimental protocol for SPECT imaging with ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO. **B.** HMPAO signal is reduced 2h after occlusion in the ipsilateral striatum and cerebral cortex. **C.** Cerebral blood flow was measured by a laser Doppler using an optical probe placed above the ipsilateral MCA. **D.** SPECT co-registration with MRI showing HMPAO signal changes after MCAo. Arrowheads indicate the ipsilateral striatum where cerebral ischemia is formed by 24h reperfusion. **E.** Time scale of HMPAO signal changes in sham animals and after MCAo. **F.** Experimental protocol for SPECT imaging with ^{99m}Tc-DTPA. **G.** Areas of BBB breakdown as revealed by detection of plasma-derived IgG leakage into the brain parenchyma on coronal brain sections overlap with increases of DTPA signal 2h and 24h after 30min MCAo (arrows). **H.** SPECT imaging with MRI co-registration showing the location of BBB injury (DTPA) within the infarct after 45min MCAo, which corresponds to leakage of plasma-derived IgG into the brain. **I.** DTPA signal 2h after experimental stroke is predictive of infarct size as measured 24h after MCAo on cresyl violet-stained brain sections. **J.** DTPA signal is significantly increased in the ipsilateral striatum 2h after MCAo compared to sham animals in mice showing infarct size larger than 20mm² 24h after stroke. **K.** 24h after MCAo DTPA signal intensity in the striatum correlates significantly with BBB injury as measured by IgG staining on brain sections. n=4-7, *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001, two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison (B, D); unpaired t test (I); linear regression (H, J).

Figure 2. Systemic inflammation reduces cerebral perfusion and rapidly augments BBB injury after experimental stroke. A-B. ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO signal is reduced significantly in the ipsilateral cerebral cortex in mice with preceding systemic inflammation (LPS + stroke) 2h after MCAo, compared to animals without systemic inflammation (stroke).

Arrowheads on SPECT / CT images showing the superficial zones of the cerebral cortex when HMPAO signal reduction is most apparent (**B**). **C**. No changes in HMPAO signal are seen in other brain areas. **D-E**. ^{99m}Tc-DTPA uptake is significantly increased in the ipsilateral hemisphere 2h after MCAo (arrowheads on **E**) in mice with preceding systemic inflammation. **F**. DTPA uptake is increased in the ipsilateral hemisphere after stroke and systemic inflammation compared to stroke mice, 24h after MCAo. **G**. DTPA in the ipsilateral striatum 2 and 24h after MCAo. n=4-5, *P<0.05, **P<0.01, P<0.001, two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison.

Figure 3. Systemic inflammation increases brain inflammation after stroke and leads to markedly impaired neurological outcome. A-B. Microglial activation (ramified, Iba1+ / CD45_{low} cells with enlarged cell body and thickened processes, arrowheads on **B**) was assessed 24h after experimental stroke in the ipsilateral hemisphere. **C**. Recruitment of CD45+ leukocytes to MCA area of the the ipsilateral cerebral cortex 24h after MCAo was markedly increased in mice with preceding systemic inflammation (arrows on **B**). **D**. Infarct size was measured on cresyl violet-stained brain sections 24h after MCAo. **E**. Mice with preceding systemic inflammation show markedly impaired neurological outcome 24h after experimental stroke. n=5-6, *P<0.05, **P<0.01, P<0.001, two-way ANOVA (**A**), unpaired t test (**C, D**) and Mann-Whitney test (**E**). Scale bar, 50µm.

Figure 4. SPECT imaging reveals early inflammatory changes in the lung after experimental stroke. A. Experimental protocol for SPECT imaging with ^{99m}Tc-HMPAO. **B**. HMPAO signal changes in the lung are evident in mice as early as 2h after experimental stroke (arrows) and mostly confined to the upper lobes of the lung as also confirmed by MRI coregistration (arrowheads). Increased lung HMPAO signal in the upper lobes of the lung is also seen 24h after MCAo (arrows). **C**. 3D reconstruction outlines affected areas in the lung

24h after MCAo. **D.** HMPAO signal in the lung is significantly different in mice after experimental stroke compared to sham animals at 24h post-surgery. **E.** I125-HSA signal is significantly increased after experimental stroke in the lung at 24h reperfusion. Quantitative analysis showing that HSA signal is significantly increased in the lung (**F**), which is most apparent in the upper lobes (**G**). **H.** Histological analysis showing inflammatory changes (alveolar space collapse, edema, arrowheads) in the upper lobes of the lung after stroke at 24h reperfusion 72h after stroke microhaemorrhages (arrows) and increased mucus production (arrowheads) are seen in the lungs as assessed on Haematoxylin and Eosin- and periodic acid-Schiff (PAS) alcian blue –stained lung sections. n=4-5, *P<0.05, **P<0.01, unpaired t test. Scale bar, 100µm.

Figure 5. SPECT imaging reveals early and transient barrier function changes in the gut after experimental stroke. **A.** Experimental protocol for SPECT imaging with 99mTc-DTPA. **B-C.** DTPA signal intensity markedly increases in the gut 2h after experimental stroke (arrowheads), which effect is abolished by 24h reperfusion. **D.** Haematoxylin and eosin staining does not show changes in the gut after experimental stroke compared to sham mice. **E.** Systemic inflammatory stimulus preceding experimental stroke results in prolonged DTPA signal increases in the gut, which are maintained up to 24h reperfusion. n=4-5, *P<0.05, unpaired t test (**C**) and two-way ANOVA followed by Sidak's multiple comparison (**E**).